

Code Book and Condensation of the Dynamic Validation Study

Moderator: Author 1

Subjects of the first session: Collaborators and practitioners of Americanas S.A.

Date: 20/09/2022

This section presents an overview of the feedback coming from the participants involved in the dynamic validation. It also contains the transcriptions and codes involved in this study.

Participants

In the following table we characterized the subjects by their role in the development of the ML-enabled systems involved in this study, educational background, and years of experience involved in ML projects. We highlighted the experienced practitioners who led each team with gray color in order to differentiate them from novice.

Team	Id	Role	Background	Experience (Years)
A	P1	Developer	Computer Science	1
	P2		Design	1
	P3		Computer Science	1.5
	P4		Computer engineering	1
	P5	Scrum Master	Physic	1.5
	P6	Data Scientist	Computer Science	1
	P7	Data Scientist	Linguistic	8
B	P8	Developer	Electronic Engineering	1
	P9		Computer Engineering	1
	P10		Computer Science	1
	P11		Mathematics	1
	P12	Scrum Master	Computer Science	2
	P13	Data Scientist	Electrical Engineering	4
	P14		Computer Science	6

We used the column 'Id' of Table II to identify the participants and their opinions. The moderator (M) of the session was the first author of the paper. We highlighted with color green the part of the text which contributes to generating the codes.

We translated the focus group to English. In the following, we outline the research questions of this study and present the code book and transcriptions.

Research Questions

- **RQ1:** What perception do practitioners have while specifying ML-enabled systems by using PerSpecML v2?
- **RQ2:** What perception do experienced practitioners have of the resulting specifications derived from PerSpecML v2?
- **RQ3:** What are the limitations and opportunities for improvement of PerSpecML v2?
- **RQ4:** To what extent do the practitioners perceive PerSpecML v2 as easy to use, useful and usable in the future?

Code Book

We identified the following list of codes attached to the transcription.

Code	Description	Type	RQ
MAPPEDACT	The diagram maps relevant activities for ML projects	Perception	RQ1
GUIDEVPROC	The approach works as a guide for ML projects	Perception	RQ1
USEFULNOV	The approach is useful for novice practitioners	Perception	RQ1
MEANFULREL	The approach has meaningful relationships	Perception	RQ1
BETTERTHANOTH	The approach is better than others	Perception	RQ2
WELLSTRUCTURE	The resulting specifications are well structured	Perception	RQ2

INFRACOST	Add financial cost involved with infrastructure	Improvement	RQ3
CLASSIFYCON	Consider classify the concerns	Improvement	RQ3
ADDOOTHEROL	Add other stakeholders such as data engineer	Improvement	RQ3
ADDPERDEGR	Add performance degradation as a concern of the model perspective	Improvement	RQ3

Code Condensations from the interviews with P7

Id	Comment	Code
M	First, thank you so much for being here. I'm going to start with a brief description of each perspective and its concerns. If you don't understand something, please let me know. You can interrupt me when you find it necessary.	
M	<i>[Here, the first perspective was introduced by the moderator: ML objectives]</i>	
P7	Before starting with the next perspective, I have one doubt. When are we going to decide if the problem we have is going to be tackled with ML techniques? In this perspective, can we know if a problem is suitable to be solved with ML techniques?	
M	We have a premise: before using our proposal, a set of resources must be evaluated. For example, a reasonable amount of data, resources such as knowledge of the technologies involved with ML, people, money, among others. On the other hand, by using our approach, the stakeholders involved in the ML project could identify that there are unresolved concerns that make it difficult to start an ML project. For example, if there are difficulties in defining ML objectives, or if data-related concerns are not clearly resolved, then there are symptoms that the problem could not be solved with ML techniques. But initially this is not part of our scope.	
P7	I asked this because ML is a fancy solution at first glance, that everyone wants to use. But maintaining and building systems with ML components is more complex than you might think.	
M	Yes, I totally agree. In fact, we seek to provide that overview so that the stakeholders can identify that landscape in the form of perspectives and concerns.	
M	<i>[Here, the second perspective was introduced by the moderator: user experience]</i>	
M	<i>[Here, the third perspective was introduced by the moderator: infrastructure]</i>	

P7	I have one doubt. When you say data streaming you are concerned with the data in operation or the data to train the model?	
M	In the data streaming concern we are concerned with the data in operation	
P7	Ok, I got it.	
P7	In my opinion, you should consider the cost of the infrastructure as a concern. In the company, we have had several experiences where infrastructure-related cost drives ML solution architectures. We have two projects that reach the objectives but depending on the infrastructure we spend more or less money. The cost is super relevant for us.	INFRACOST
M	<i>[Here, the fourth perspective was introduced by the moderator: model]</i>	
M	<i>[Here, the fifth perspective was introduced by the moderator: data]</i>	
P7	Talking about data in ML contexts is very complex. I understand the data taxonomy divided into training, validation and test. But I feel a lack of definitions about the operational data, I mean, when do I know if the operational data represents the behavior of the model?	
M	In that sense, we have two concerns in the data perspective that can help: the completeness of the data that seeks to guarantee that data contains sufficient observations of all situations where the model will operate. On the other hand, we also have the real usage concern that is the need to get real data representing the real problem.	
M	<i>[Here, the perspective-based ML task and concern diagram was introduced by the moderator]</i>	
M	<i>[Here, the specifications of the two projects derived from PerSpecML were presented by the moderator]</i>	
M	Now we want to hear from you about PerSpecML and the specification we derived from it. What is your opinion about the approach? Do you think that PerSpecML helped to specify the ML-enabled system?	
P7	I am not sure if the specifications are already sufficiently clear, but I can state what has been raised is reasonable and useful. Coming up with a clear specification requires refinements and increments. Overall, the approach is good. The diagram and the specification template helped us a lot. PerSpecML provides a more comprehensive overview and is far better than the ML canvas, which is the artifact we currently use to specify systems with ML components.	BETTERTHANOTH
P7	On its practical use, there are many concerns that should be considered. It worries me to have to analyze so many aspects but at the same time I consider that the landscape that PerSpecML offers is	CLASSIFYCONCERNS

	very complete. My point is to what extent the solution becomes complex. In my opinion, the diagram can give a vision of what could be prioritized and analyzed first.	
M	Good point, we will provide some light about it. Thank you so much for pointing out this.	

Code Condensations from the interviews with P13 and P14

Id	Comment	Code
M	We are so glad to have you all today to talk about PerSpecML and the specifications of the two projects we specified by using PerSpecML. First, I'm going to present a brief description of each perspective and its concerns. If you don't understand something, please let me know. You can interrupt me when you find it necessary.	
M	<i>[Here, the first perspective was introduced by the moderator: ML objectives]</i>	
M	<i>[Here, the second perspective was introduced by the moderator: user experience]</i>	
M	<i>[Here, the third perspective was introduced by the moderator: infrastructure]</i>	
M	Well, any questions or comments so far?	
P13	Yes, looking at the relationships I can see the following: linking the model update task in the infrastructure perspective with the need to get user feedback in the user experience perspective makes sense	MEANFULREL
P14	Another comment, we don't just have software engineers and data scientists here. We also have data engineers, ML engineers, and cloud engineers, who perform many of the tasks involved in this perspective. It may happen that other companies have a different functional organization and those stakeholders do not always apply. So, I think it would be good to make this clear.	ADDOTHEROL
M	<i>[Here, the fourth perspective was introduced by the moderator: model]</i>	
P13	All the concerns you explained are good aspects we should analyze, but I think you are missing a concern in this perspective: Performance degradation is typically something that even data scientists don't discuss in ML projects. In fact, this is something that should be explained to customers because it is something that will affect them over time.	ADDPERDEGR

M	Sure, it makes sense for us. Thank you for pointing this out.	
M	<i>[Here, the fifth perspective was introduced by the moderator: data]</i>	
M	Any questions or comments regarding the data perspective?	
M	<i>[Here, the specifications of the two projects derived from PerSpecML were presented by the moderator]</i>	
M	Thank you for paying attention and participating in the discussion. Now we want to hear from you about PerSpecML and the specification we derived from it. Do you think that PerSpecML helped to specify the ML-enabled system?	
P13	I'm very satisfied with the results of the specifications of both projects. Several concerns were addressed and this is really helpful.	MAPPEDACT
P14	In addition, many times in our projects some of these concerns are only addressed when it is clearly too late. I see the diagram as a roadmap that allows me to identify components that would not be identified without its use.	GUIDEVPROC
P13	The specifications demonstrated a good understanding of the ML projects' requirements, guiding the novice practitioners through the specification process.	WELLSTRUCTURE
P2	I found the approach you proposed very useful. There are several tasks that at the beginning of the project do not concern our team, but that deserve to be analyzed for their relationships with others.	
P2	Looking at the diagram of PerSpecML, it summarizes the work of various ML teams.	MEANFULREL
M	Do you think that PerSpecML can be useful in practice?	
P14	Absolutely yes. Currently, we use ML canvas to describe ML systems, but PerSpecML covers more elements, and helps analyze their relationships. In that sense, we would benefit from the approach. In addition, the results of the specification were positive, in my opinion.	BETTERTHANOTH
M	Nice. P13, do you want to say something?	
P13	Yes. I see the diagram could be extremely helpful for novice data scientists or engineers since it gets an overview of the ML workflow. In my opinion, that is outstanding.	USEFULNOV
P13	However, I would like to suggest an improvement. it would be interesting to classify each concern by its importance. Why do I say	CLASSIFYCON

	this? Looking at the diagram I see too many concerns that maybe can be confused at a first sight.	
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